

Investigating Tourists' Attitude and Intention to Visit Resorts in Bangladesh: An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract

Purpose: This study intends to investigate the predictors of tourists' attitude and intention to visit resorts in the context of Bangladesh.

Design/Approach/Methodology: A quantitative research design has been followed in this study. In doing so, the researchers used a cross-sectional survey method to collect responses from 373 respondents using judgmental sampling technique. A research model was developed based on the principles of behavioral reasoning theory. Besides, the research model's reliability, validity, and hypotheses were tested using partial least square based structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM).

Findings: This study confirmed that physical environment of resorts, tourists' perception of price justice, and perceived security positively influence tourists' attitudes toward visiting resorts. Surprisingly, the authors found that perceived crowdedness positively influences tourist attitude. Moreover, contrary to the researchers believe, the study demonstrated that health & hygiene risks do not contribute significantly to tourist attitude. In addition, it was found that positive tourist attitude leads to stronger intention to visit resorts. Furthermore, this study revealed that physical environment, perceived price justice, and perceived security indirectly affects visit intention through customer attitude.

Practical Implications: The outputs and implications presented in this study will stimulate the stakeholders to focus on improving the resorts' physical environment. Moreover, this study presents how to use several bundle pricing methods to ensure price justice to influence tourist attitude. Besides, this study details the security steps resorts authorities should ensure from guest check-in till check-out.

Originality: To the best of the researchers' knowledge, this study has been one of the first attempts to explain the predictors of tourist attitude and behavioral intention in the resorts of Bangladesh by applying and validating behavioral reasoning theory.

Keywords: Attitude, Intention, Behavioral Reasoning Theory, Physical Environment, Resort

1. Introduction

The concepts of tourist attitude and behavioral intention have received significant academic and practical attention in recent years, contributing substantially to the tourism literature and practice (Eid et al., 2021; Demir et al., 2021). Scholars agree that insights into tourists' attitudes and behavioral patterns enable tourism marketers to make sound marketing decisions required to develop, sell, and promote tourism products (Swarbrooke & Horner,

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2007). In the tourism and hospitality industry, resorts are among the dominant subcategories, catering to tourists' travel and tourism demands (Ahn & Back, 2018). In recent days, an increasing number of tourists visit resorts located in aesthetically appealing destinations to receive entertaining, esthetic, and escapism experiences. According to Gee (2000), a resort hotel contains adequate interior facilities, comfortable & clean physical atmosphere, entertainment & leisure amenities, exclusive location, climate, and landscapes.

Today, resorts emphasize gaining favorable attitudes and behavioral intentions of their guests to ensure greater frequency of visits, enhanced customer satisfaction, and favorable word of mouth behavior (Ali et al., 2016). Thus, marketers should investigate the determinants that may lead to favorable tourist attitudes and visit intention in the resort hotel setting. Past studies have reported several reasons for positive tourists' attitudes and behavioral intention in hospitality attractions, including servicescape elements/physical environment quality (Hwang & Ok, 2013), price perceptions (Khare et al., 2014; Cakici et al., 2019) and perceived safety/security (Moon et al., 2017), service quality (Bappy & Samiya, 2018), destination image (Bappy, 2019), and many more.

However, most of these studies are dominated by western and developed hospitality cultures. Thus, the external validity of these studies requires further testing from the perspective of a non-western emerging economy, where the tourism/resort industry is still at a nascent stage. Moreover, existing tourist behavior studies have been conducted before the outbreak of Covid-19 crisis, which has resulted in significant transformation in the tourist attitudinal and behavioral patterns. Today, tourists are emphasizing health & hygiene issues (Su et al., 2021). On top of that, health experts are also recommending the tourists to avoid crowded locations, such as parks, beaches, and resorts, because of greater perceived health and hygiene risks (WTO, 2020). Hence, understanding if perceived crowdedness and perceived health & hygiene risks are strong reasons against tourists' attitude and behavioral intention has become a subject of investigation in the crisis-affected hospitality setting (Milman et al., 2020; Su et al., 2021).

This study considered selected resorts of Bangladesh as the research context. The resort industry in Bangladesh has experienced notable growth in the last 10 years, leading to a favorable impact on the domestic tourist sector (Siddiqui, 2020). According to Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation, the country presently has around 300 resorts, and the market size of the overall resort industry is around 3000 crores (Siddiqui, 2020). However, despite the rising prominence, resorts have remained one of the most under-researched areas in the hospitality sector, globally and in Bangladesh (Line & Runyan, 2012; Ali, 2015). From the perspective of Bangladesh, only a handful pieces of literature focused on the resort industry (Emma, 2012; Ashraf & Himel, 2017; Kabir & Shetu, 2020), but those studies did not identify both the reasons for and against tourist attitude and behavioral intention in a holistic model. Thus, researchers believe that an integrated model explaining the reasons for and against positive/negative tourists' attitudes and behavioral intention will add value to tourism literature and practice in the new normal era.

Therefore, the purpose of this research is to investigate several research questions: i) what are the reasons for and against positive/negative tourists' attitudes toward visiting resorts? ii) What is the role of attitude in influencing tourists' intention to visit resorts? iii) Do

physical environment, perceived price justice, perceived security, perceived crowdedness, and perceived health & hygiene risks indirectly affect tourists' intention to visit resorts through tourist attitude. To address these research questions, the authors have adopted the principles of behavioral reasoning theory because of its holistic nature and predictive utility.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Background

This study has adopted the behavioral reasoning theory (BRT) to explain the reasons for/against tourists' positive/negative attitude and subsequent behavioral intention (Westaby, 2005). According to this theory, individual behavior is shaped by global motives (such as, attitude) whereas attitude is shaped by several reasons for and against performing that behavior (Westaby, 2005). That is to say, reasons act as significant connectors between beliefs, global motives (e.g., attitudes), intentions, and behavior. A fundamental hypothetical postulation of this is model that reasons affect attitudes and intentions as they facilitate a person to validate as well as support their activities (Westaby, 2005).

This theory is based on the principles of two noteworthy theories (such as, theory of reasoned action and the theory of planned). The reason for choosing this theory is twofold. First, while previous behavioral theories focused only on the positive determinants of behavioral intention, BRT explains the factors that have both positive and negative influence on the behavior (Tandon et al., 2020). Second, BRT is a broad & comprehensive theory that allowed the researchers to incorporate context specific factors in this study to holistically predict tourists' intention to visit resorts.

In light of prior pieces of literature, this study considers physical environment, perceived price justice, and perceived security as the reasons for developing positive attitude and attitude and intention to visit resorts (Ali & Amin, 2014; Cakici et al., 2019; Moon et al., 2017). On the contrary, based on previous empirical studies, the authors regarded perceived crowdedness and perceived health and hygiene risk as the reasons against developing positive attitude and intention to visit resorts (Milman et al., 2020; Su et al., 2021).

Table 1 *Conceptual Definition of the Constructs*

Constructs	Conceptual Definition
Physical Environment	Physical environment refers to the physical and human atmosphere, including the resort design, décor, landscape, layout, ambiance, and service staff, in which resort services are delivered to the guests (Ali et al., 2016).
Perceived Price Justice	Perceived price justice denotes how much guests consider the prices of resort services to be fair and reasonable (Cakici et al., 2019).
Perceived Safety	In this study, perceived safety indicates the extent to which tourists find it safe and secured to visit a resort hotel (George, 2003).
Perceived Crowdedness	Perceived crowding indicates the difficulties/stress encountered by the tourists due to extreme number of participants in the resort settings (Milman et al., 2020).
Perceived Health & Hygiene Risks	It indicates the degree to which tourists feel that visiting a resort hotel will result in unfavorable health & hygiene issues (Su et al., 2021)

Constructs	Conceptual Definition
Attitude toward Visiting	Attitude toward visiting indicates the degree to which tourists' believe that visiting a resort hotel will result in favorable outcomes (Ginanjari & Hurriyati, 2019).
Intention to Visit	Intention to visit refers to the probability that tourists' will visit a resort hotel in the future (Ginanjari & Hurriyati, 2019).

2.2 Studies on Tourists' attitude and behavioral Intention in Resort

This study reviewed several relevant studies related to tourists' attitude and intention to visit resorts both during and before Covid-19 pandemic. The summary of those studies are presented below:

Table 2: Summary of Literature on Tourists' Attitude and Behavioral Intention in Resort

Authors	Objective	Context	Period	Findings
Ali & Amin (2014)	To evaluate the factors affecting resort visitors' behavioral intention	China	Pre-Covid	Visitors having favorable perceptions about resorts' physical environment have greater probability of having positive emotions, increasing satisfaction level and intention to visit.
Ali & Omar (2014)	To examine the determinants of customer experience and consequent visitors' satisfaction and behavioral intention in resort	Malaysia	Pre-Covid	Physical ambience and social environments are strong antecedents of customer experience, resulting in visitors' satisfaction as well as revisit intentions at the Malaysian resorts
Ali (2015)	To investigate the role of service quality in enhancing customer attitude and resulting behavioral intention in resort setting	Malaysia	Pre-Covid	Favorable perceptions about resort environment and employee courtesy, food and beverage products, employee performance and knowledge, reservation services and financial value have positive relationships with customer attitude which, in turn, lead to greater intention to visit and recommend resorts.
Pham Minh & Ngoc Mai (2021)	To evaluate how Covid-19 has affected resort hotel booking intention	Vietnam	During-Covid	Covid-19 knowledge enhances general tourists' perceived risk; causing an unfavorable impact on their resort hotel booking intention
Quan et al. (2022)	To investigate tourists' financial risk perception and attitude in the resort hotel setting	China	During-Covid	Protective measures against Covid-19 have substantial effect on financial risk perceptions, attitude, which consequently have a role in customer satisfaction and behavioral intention.

The Table 3 shows the studies on tourism crisis due to pandemic and its subsequence effect on tourist behavior.

Table 3: Tourism Crisis Literature

Authors	Context	Objectives	Major Findings
Laparojkit & Suttipun (2021)	Thailand	The major objective was to inspect the effect of trust and customer loyalty on the customer's intention to revisit in the coastal tourism in Thailand.	Researchers found significant level of trust, loyalty and intention to revisit the coastal regions during the Covid-19 Pandemic by the local tourists.
Polukhina et al. (2021)	Russia	The study's overall objective was to identify strategies for promoting sustainable rural tourism in Russian regions and to develop indicators for assessing the effectiveness of local strategic development programs, during Covid-19 crisis.	The findings indicated flaws in federal and local policies, including a lack of systemic steps to improve the sustainability of Russian tourism sites.
Riestyaningrum et al. (2020)	China	Evaluating the effect of Covid-19 on Chinese international tourists' behavior in the face of crises to their commitment to travel abroad when the epidemic is finished.	There is a significant partial effect of attitude, tourist's preferences, hygiene and safety found on their intention to travel abroad.
Li et al. (2018)	China	Effect of harm crises on the travel intention.	The risk and legitimacy have a significant negative impact on travel intention.
Mansour et al. (2019)	Libya	Determine the specific sorts of adaptable solutions that enabled tour operators to survive the crisis caused by the civil war in Libya	The study sums up that, the continuous exchange between businesses and their settings, as well as the particular steps taken by managers and employees, are essential for the sustainability and adaptability of businesses to new contexts and circumstances.

2.3 Hypothesis Development

2.3.1 Physical Environment and Attitude

The role of physical environment in influencing consumer behavior in the resort hotel setting is well documented in the extant studies (Ali et al., 2013; Ali & Amin, 2014; Ali, 2015). Studies on customer behavior and psychology suggest that customers tend to respond on the physical surroundings emotionally and cognitively (Bitner, 1992). Scholars in the past have pointed out that several aspects of physical atmosphere, such as layout, aesthetics, cleanliness, color, light, temperature, decorations and artifacts, are the reasons why tourists form favorable hedonic attitude toward a hospitality setting, (Chun & Roh, 2005; Hwang & Ok, 2013). However, to the best of authors' knowledge, no empirical study has studied the relationship between physical environment and attitude in the context of Bangladeshi

resort setting although an understanding of such relationship will assist resort marketers in their decision-making process. Thus, in light of previous studies, this research hypothesizes:

H₁: Physical environment is positively related to attitude toward visiting resorts.

2.3.2 Perceived Price Justice and Attitude

Individuals tend to base their decision on their perceptions of prices while evaluating the intangible services (Han & Ryu, 2009). Scholars have categorized resorts under the service business (Tsiotsou & Goldsmith, 2012). According to Mattila & O'Neill (2003), price can be considered a strong indicator of resorts' service quality. Moreover, extant scholarly works demonstrate that if tourists regard the prices of tourism & hospitality services fair, reasonable & acceptable, they develop a favorable mindset to visit the destination (Chang & Chang, 2015; Cakici et al., 2019). This logic is also supported by equity theory, which was proposed by Adams in 1965 (Cakici et al., 2019). Therefore, the following hypothesis can be suggested in light of aforementioned arguments:

H₂: Perceived price justice is positively related to attitude toward visiting resorts.

2.3.3 Perceived Safety and Attitude

The role of perceived safety in shaping tourists' attitude and decision to initiate a tour has previously been a subject of academic attention (George, 2003; Calderon, 2013). It has been argued that because of a greater degree of safety concerns, such as physical and verbal assaults, fear of terrorism, political unrest, theft, health issues, privacy concerns, and natural disasters, tourists' generally form an unfavorable attitude toward visiting a destination (Calderon, 2013). Alternatively, evidence suggests that a higher level of perceived safety lowers perceived travel risks, leading to a positive attitude and visit intention (Xie et al., 2020). In Bangladesh, it was revealed that tourists consider security issues on a priority basis for their choice of resorts to stay (Al Muneem & Ananya, 2020). Therefore, the authors postulate:

H₃: Perceived safety is positively related to attitude toward visiting resorts.

2.3.4 Perceived Crowding and Attitude

Several studies in the past have studied the influence of both human and spatial crowding on consumer behavior in the tourism, leisure and hospitality service sector (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2016; Liu & Ma, 2019). According to Milman et al. (2020), overcrowding is one of the reasons that have a negative effect on tourist mindset in several tourism attractions like museums, theme parks, and resorts. On the other hand, in certain tourism and hospitality settings, such as concerts, sports, or restaurants, a greater number of crowds may result in positive consumer attitudes (Thomas & Saenger, 2019). However, during the Covid-19 period, consumers have become health conscious and are being asked to avoid crowded locations. Thus, it is expected that a greater number of crowds will deter them from visiting tourist attractions like resorts. On that note, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

H₄: Perceived crowding is negatively related to attitude toward visiting resorts.

2.3.5 *Perceived Health & Hygiene Risks and Attitude*

Covid-19 pandemic has brought a dramatic slab on the tourism industry world widely. Many tourist destinations had to close down to prevent the spread of coronavirus over the last one and a half year. Health and hygiene risks have now become a major challenge for the resorts and amusement parks. Social distancing, maintenance of hygiene factors, and attendance of governmental regulations are now become a compulsory movement for resorts and tourism spots to establish customer confidence and promote themselves as a health-conscious entity (Quan et al., 2021). Therefore, health and hygiene risks are likely to have an adverse effect on customer attitude toward visiting tourism attractions during this pandemic in several nations (Yin et al. 2020; Korea Herald, 2020; Su et al., 2021). Thus, we come to the following hypotheses

H₅: Perceived health & hygiene risks are negatively related to attitude toward visiting resorts.

2.3.6 *Customers' attitude and intention*

Attitude toward visiting is treated as one of the major drivers of consumers' intention to consumer a product of service (Popy & Bappy, 2020). Several widely recognized models, such as the theory of reasoned action, the theory of planned behavior, and technology acceptance model, have provided empirical evidence about the positive relationship between attitude and intention (Ajzen, 2020; Himel et al., 2021). In the tourism & hospitality setting, it has previously been found that tourists' positive mindset/attitude toward visiting a tourist attraction prompts them to demonstrate stronger willingness to visit that attraction (Han et al., 2010; Chen & Tung; 2014; Ulker-Demirel & Ciftci, 2020). Hence, following hypothesis is proposed:

H₆: Attitude toward visiting is positively related to intention to visit resorts

2.3.7 *Mediating Role of Attitude*

In many tourism and hospitality studies, attitude served the role of a mediator in the relationship between its predictors and intention (Doosti et al., 2016; Patwary et al., 2021). Previously, several studies found the direct relationship of physical environment, price justice, perceived safety/security, perceived crowding, and health & hygiene risks with intention (George, 2003; Ali et al., 2016; Cakici et al., 2019; Milman et al., 2020; Su et al., 2021). Besides, the relationship between attitude and intention in the tourism context is well documented in the existing literature (Ajzen and Driver, 1992). Furthermore, the literature supporting the relationship of physical environment, price justice, perceived safety/security, perceived crowding, and health & hygiene risks with consumer attitude has already been reported in the preceding sections. Thus, this study hypothesizes:

H₇: Attitude toward visiting mediates:

- a) The positive relationship between physical environment and intention
- b) The positive relationship between perceived price justice and intention
- c) The positive relationship between perceived safety and intention
- d) The negative relationship between perceived crowding and intention
- e) The negative relationship between health & hygiene risk and intention

Considering the aforementioned hypotheses, this study has developed the research model demonstrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: *Research Model*

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study was quantitative in nature where the authors used a cross sectional survey to conduct this study. In a cross-sectional survey, information is sought from the respondents only once (Malhotra and Das, 2015; Bappy and Haque, 2018). This research design was preferred because it is more suitable for choosing representative sampling and avoiding response bias (Malhotra and Das, 2015). Besides, this method is comparatively inexpensive and less-time consuming than the other methods of research.

3.2 Measurement

The authors used several scales to measure the latent constructs shown in Figure 1. The term “latent construct” indicates an unobservable concept that can be conceptualized but cannot be evaluated directly (Malhotra et al., 2015). Therefore, such constructs are measured by several indicators or items. The construct “physical environment” was evaluated with five items and they were adapted from Ali & Amin (2014). Four indicators for evaluating the construct “perceived price justice” were extracted from Ali & Amin (2014) and Cakici et al. (2019). The construct “perceived safety” was evaluated with five items extracted from George (2003). Moreover, “perceived crowding” construct was measured with three indicators drawn from Milman et al. (2020). Besides, “health & hygiene risks” construct was evaluated with three items adapted from Su et al. (2020). Finally, items used to measure the constructs, such as “attitude” and “intention”, were adapted from Ajzen & Driver (1992). Items of each constructs including the sources are given in the Appendix 1.

To ensure content validity of the scale items, the researchers conducted a pre-testing with 4 academicians and 3 professionals. Upon receiving their remarks, several items were somewhat edited according to the context of the present study. Besides, the scales were pilot

tested with 38 respondents. All the scale items were found to have satisfactory internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha above .7). Besides, previous scholars also validated these scales (Ajzen & Driver, 1992; George, 2003; Ali & Amin, 2014; Cakici et al., 2019; Milman et al., 2020). Hence, the authors believe that the items chosen in this study are reasonable. The indicators were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, whose anchors ranged from “*strongly disagree*” to “*strongly agree*”. Although seven/ten-point scales are familiar in hospitality studies, the researchers have decided to choose 5-point scale because scales with too many options sometimes disturb the respondents. Besides, the difference between the data points is sometimes meaningless in a Likert-type scale with lots of categories. In many cases, the difference between “somewhat agree” and “likely to agree” is extremely little (Sarstedt & Mooi, 2014). Hence, the respondents might not even be able to differentiate the data points (Bappy et al., 2020). Therefore, considering the respondents' background, the preference of 5-point scale seems logical.

3.3 Sampling Plan

The target population of this study includes tourists aged 18 or above who have visited at least one resort from Gazipur, Cox's Bazar, or Rangpur Division at least once in the years between July 2019 and July 2021. The reason for choosing the last three years is because the researchers are more willing to investigate the tourists' attitudinal and behavioral pattern in both prior and during pandemic. This study considered the resorts of Gazipur and Cox's Bazar and Rangpur Division as our research setting since majority of the resorts in Bangladesh are located in these areas.

The sample size was 373 and they were chosen using judgmental sampling technique. The judgmental non-probability sampling was chosen because of the scarcity of sampling frame (Bappy & Chowdhury, 2020). In order to calculate sample size, the authors used 10 times rule of thumb suggested by Hair et al (2017). As per this rule, sample size should be 10 times the total number of items. This study has used 30 items in total. Besides, previous scholars have proposed that any sample size above 200 is a “critical sample size” (Memon et al., 2020). Thus, this study's sample size of 373 surpasses the threshold levels.

3.4 Time Frame of Data Collection and Data Collection Methods:

The primary data were collected between June 2021 and September 2021 using survey method whereas the secondary information was collected from journals, newspapers, articles, many more.

3.5 Data Analysis Tools & Techniques

This study performed frequency distribution analysis using SPSS. SPSS was chosen because of its availability and ease of use (Field, 2013). Moreover, partial least square based structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using Smart-PLS version 3.9 was utilized to assess the measurement model and to test the hypotheses of this study. This statistical technique was preferred because it has greater predictive utility, works with non-normal data as well as with smaller sample size (Hair Jr et al., 2017)

4 Findings

4.1 Demographic Profile

Table 4 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. This study evaluated the respondents' age group, profession, traveler type, and travel frequency in the last three years. The results show that most of the respondents are female (188), belong to the 26-35 age group (165), are entry-level job holder (168), have only domestic travel experience (260), and made less than five visits in the preceding three years (142).

Table 4: *Demographic Profile*

Age group	Gender		Total
	Female (188)	Male (185)	
18-25	26	23	49
26-35	82	83	165
36-45	64	68	132
45-60	9	7	16
60+	7	4	11
Profession			
Students	26	20	46
Not engaged with any job	53	21	74
Entry-level job	72	96	168
Mid-level job	23	36	59
Top level job	7	10	17
Retired	7	2	9
Travel Experience			
Only national	157	103	260
National and International	31	82	113
Travel frequency in the last three years (July 2019-July 2021)			
At least ten visits in the last three years	32	84	116
At least five visits in the last three years	35	54	89
Less than five visits in the last three years	110	32	142
Did not visit any hotels and resorts the last three years	11	15	26

4.2 Assessing Measurement Model

The authors first evaluated the reliability and validity of the measurement model by employing the confirmatory factor analysis. The research model demonstrated in Figure 1 includes five reflective exogenous constructs, one reflective mediator construct and one reflective endogenous construct.

“Exogenous construct is the unobserved, multi-item equivalent of an independent variable which is measured by multiple variables” (Malhotra & Das, 2015) while an “endogenous construct is the unobserved, multi-item equivalent of an independent variable” (Malhotra

& Das, 2015). Besides, a mediator construct is a mechanism through which exogenous construct affects the endogenous construct (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2021).

Table 5 presents the findings of CFA, indicating acceptable reliability scores since the latent constructs' Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values are above the threshold level of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019; Bappy et al., 2020). Moreover, the average variance extracted (AVE) of all underlying dimensions turned out to be greater than the satisfactory level of 0.5, and item loadings were higher than 0.7, suggesting adequate convergent validity of those dimensions (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 5: *Measurement model (CFA)*

	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Physical Environment	PHE1	0.775	0.825	0.877	0.588
	PHE2	0.767			
	PHE3	0.770			
	PHE4	0.775			
	PHE5	0.748			
Perceived Price Justice	PPJ1	0.893	0.903	0.932	0.775
	PPJ2	0.874			
	PPJ3	0.874			
	PPJ4	0.880			
Perceived Safety	PS1	0.804	0.866	0.903	0.652
	PS2	0.825			
	PS3	0.843			
	PS4	0.771			
	PS5	0.791			
Perceived Crowding	CRD1	0.932	0.870	0.900	0.753
	CRD2	0.905			
	CRD3	0.755			
Health & Hygiene risk	HHR2	0.844	0.910	0.931	0.818
	HHR3	0.978			
	HHR4	0.886			
Attitude	ATT1	0.833	0.876	0.915	0.729
	ATT2	0.871			
	ATT3	0.867			
	ATT4	0.843			
Intention	INT1	0.791	0.892	0.918	0.650
	INT2	0.760			
	INT3	0.830			
	INT4	0.788			
	INT5	0.849			
	INT6	0.816			

Discriminant validity test was also conducted to evaluate whether the measure of construct related to each other or not (Hair et al., 2013; Fornell & Larcker, 1981). This study assessed the discriminant validity using the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) ratio as it is proven as an efficient method through Monte Carlo simulation (Henseler et al., 2015). Based on the HTMT ratio presented in Table 6, it is evident that all the constructs have HTMT ratio less than 0.85 as recommended in several studies for theoretically different constructs (Hair et al., 2019; Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 6: Discriminant Validity (HTMT Criterion)

	ATT	CRD	HHR	INT	PPJ	PS	PHE
ATT							
CRD	0.088						
HHR	0.07	0.085					
INT	0.52	0.073	0.149				
PPJ	0.706	0.232	0.066	0.298			
PS	0.573	0.387	0.077	0.225	0.778		
PHE	0.619	0.449	0.062	0.189	0.77	0.713	

Legends: ATT= Attitude, CRD= Crowdedness, HHR= Health & Hygiene Risk, INT= Intention, PPJ= Perceived Price Justice, PS= Perceived Security, PHE= Physical Environment

4.3 Assessing the Structural Model

In this phase of this study, the authors assessed the structural model to test the hypotheses of this study. This study found that R^2 values for endogenous constructs, such as attitude toward visiting and intention to visit resorts, were 0.503 and 0.388, respectively, revealing a reasonable level of in-sample explanatory power in social science research (Hair et al., 2019; Himel et al., 2021).

Next, the researchers performed bootstrapping using 5000 samples to gauge this study's hypotheses. As shown in Figure 2 and Table 7, the relationship between PHE and ATT was positive and significant ($\beta=.286$, $t = 3.978$). Thus, H_1 was supported. Similarly, the paths from PPJ to ATT ($\beta=.376$, $t = 3.978$) and PS to ATT ($\beta=.160$, $t = 3.978$), and ATT and INT ($\beta=.461$, $t = 8.578$) were positive and statistically significant. Hence, H_2 and H_3 , and H_6 were also supported.

However, although the relationship between PC and ATT was statistically significant and the direct of the path coefficient was positive ($\beta=.308$, $t = 3.417$) rather than negative. Since, this research expected a negative relationship between PC and ATT, the H_4 was not supported. Additionally, PHHR had negative but insignificant effect on ATT ($\beta= -.040$, $t = 0.933$). Thus, H_5 was not supported.

Furthermore, this study used product of coefficient method (Hayes & Scharkaw, 2013) of mediation to evaluate the indirect effects of physical environment, perceived price justice, perceived safety, perceived crowding, and perceived health & hygiene risks on tourists' intention to visit through attitude. As shown in Table 8, attitude mediates in the relationship of physical environment, perceived price justice, and perceived safety with intention

because specific indirect effect of these three paths were statistically significant and zero did not straddle between the lower level and upper level confidence intervals, indicating strong evidence for mediation (Himel et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2010). As a result, H₇ (a–c) have been supported.

H₇ (d) hypothesized that attitude mediates the negative relationship between crowding and intention. However, this study found that attitude is a mediator in the positive relationship between crowding and intention, which is contrary to H₇ (d). Hence, H₇ (d) was not supported. Finally, since zero appeared in between the lower level and upper confidence intervals for the path PHHR -> ATT -> INT, H₇ (e) was not supported. Hence, it can be concluded that the relationship between health risks and intention to visit is not mediated by attitude toward visiting.

Figure 2: Structural Model Results

Table 7: Path coefficient

	Paths	Beta	Std error	t	5% LLCI	95% ULCI	p values	Results
H ₁	PHE -> ATT	0.286	0.072	3.978	0.178	0.411	0.000	Supported
H ₂	PPJ -> ATT	0.376	0.075	5.010	0.250	0.496	0.000	Supported
H ₃	PS -> ATT	0.160	0.067	2.392	0.056	0.274	0.008	Supported
H ₄	PC -> ATT	0.308	0.090	3.417	0.147	0.401	0.000	Not Supported
H ₅	PHHR -> ATT	-0.040	0.042	0.933	-0.100	0.042	0.175	Not Supported
H ₆	ATT -> INT	0.461	0.054	8.578	0.367	0.544	0.000	Supported

Legends: ATT= Attitude, PC= Perceived Crowding, PHHR= Perceived Health & Hygiene Risk, INT= Intention, PPJ= Perceived Price Justice, PS= Perceived Security, PHE= Physical Environment

Table 8: *Specific Indirect Effects*

	Paths	Beta	Std error	T	5% LLCI	95% ULCI	p values	Results
H _{7a}	PHE -> ATT -> INT	0.132	0.036	3.702	0.081	0.200	0.000	Supported
H _{7b}	PPJ -> ATT -> INT	0.173	0.041	4.262	0.107	0.239	0.000	Supported
H _{7c}	PS -> ATT -> INT	0.074	0.032	2.287	0.026	0.132	0.011	Supported
H _{7d}	PC -> ATT -> INT	0.142	0.046	3.122	0.067	0.205	0.001	Not Supported
H _{7e}	PHHR -> ATT -> INT	-0.018	0.020	0.918	-0.047	0.020	0.179	Not Supported

5. Discussions

This study aimed to explore the antecedents of tourists' attitude and resulting behavioral intention in resorts of Bangladesh. The paper found that physical environment has positive effect on tourists' attitude toward visiting resorts. This result is in consistent with prior scholarly works conducted by Ali et al. (2013) and Han & Ryu (2009). Hence, all else being equal, if quality of physical environment is found satisfactory, tourists are more likely to have positive attitude toward visiting the resorts.

Though several studies showed less effect of price justice on the tourists' attitude and intention to visit tourism sector (Isa et al., 2018; Campo & Yagüe, 2008), the present study suggests otherwise. Based on this study's findings, perceived price justice of the tourists has a significant impact on their attitude and intention to visit. Our insights explicate that the most of the people in Bangladesh shows price sensitive behavior unlike the results from other countries like Malaysia, Taiwan, Spain etc (Isa et al., 2018; Jia-Jan et al., 2018; Perles et al., 2018). On the contrary, resort authorities added that it is extremely tough for them to manage their financials as tourist traffics are not same over the year. Thus, this study's authors recommend the implementation of seasonal pricing strategy for the resorts so that price sensitive tourists can visit their preferred destinations at a low price in the off-pick seasons.

According to the study findings, perceived safety and security have a significant effect on the tourist attitude as well as intention to visit resorts. Similar studies showed parallel results studied in other countries well like India, China, Ghana etc. (Hole et al, 2019; Shih-Chieh et al, 2017; Poku, 2016). Therefore, if tourists' safety and security are ensured, they will have favorable attitude toward visiting resorts.

Moreover, this study found that perceived crowdedness positively affects visitors' attitude, which was contrary to the researchers' expectations and previous study conducted by Milman et al. (2020). Though the result was very surprising but it explains one of the unique characteristics of Bangladeshi tourists. Bangladeshi is a collectivist society where tourists prefer visiting crowded locations. Previously, some scholars found that crowded tourism & hospitality destinations are sometimes perceived as popular. Thus, because of such perceived popularity, tourists' form a positive attitude towards those crowded tourism attractions. Hence, this study found positive relationship between perceived crowding and

attitude toward visiting resorts. In addition, the relationship between perceived health & hygiene risks did not have significant influence on tourists' attitude toward resorts.

Besides, the study results illustrated that perceived health and hygiene risks do not significantly affect visitors' attitude unlike the other prior studies (Quan et al., 2021; Schuckert et al., 2021). One of the reasons is that tourists were restricted in their homes during two phases of lockdown due to Covid-19. With the mass vaccination, individuals are getting less conscious with health and hygiene risks. Presently, tourists want to explore some natural beauties and fresh air in the tourist destinations. Therefore, this study did not find significant negative relationship between perceived health & hygiene risks and attitude toward visiting. The observed outputs of this study strengthen our perception that attitude toward visiting is the pathway by which the key exogenous constructs (viz. physical environment, perceived price justice, and perceived safety) are able to affect a tourist's intent to visit a resort hotel. These findings are in line with some related previous studies conducted by (Ali et al., 2013; Han & Ryu, 2009; Calderon, 2013; Rasoolimanesh et al., 2016; Quan et al., 2021; Popy & Bappy, 2020).

6. Implications

6.1 Theoretical Implications

This research validates the existing tourist attitude and behavioral intention literature through the lenses of behavioral reasoning theory (BRT). Extant studies regarding tourist attitude and intention do not explore determinants for and against tourist attitude & visiting intention in one single research model. This study takes one of the very few deliberate endeavors to explore the factors affecting tourist attitude and behavioral intention in resorts deploying behavioral reasoning theory mentioning both, reasons for and reasons against, which makes a significant theoretical contribution. This study also adds Covid-19 context specific factors in the BRT framework— such as Health and hygiene risk (Mani & Chouk, 2018) and perceived crowdedness (Mani & Chouk, 2018), which contributed to the model's explanatory power and predictive relevance.

6.2 Practical Implications:

This study will motivate resort practitioners to adopt several marketing strategies. Inspired by the positive and significant relationship of physical environment with tourists' attitude and intention, the resort marketers will be encouraged to improve the quality of physical environmental aspects of the resorts, such as landscapes, layouts, colors, interior & exterior design, temperature, décor, dress up of the service staff, and others.

Moreover, encouraged by the positive and significant relationship of perceived price justice with tourists' attitude and intention, the resort marketers may come up with attractive pricing offers, such as bundling several offers into a single reduced price and provide discounts, free coupons, redeemable points, as well as cash back offers because such strategies can make the tourists perceive that the room rate and food price at the resorts acceptable. In short, the resort marketers should deliver on their promises to make their price seem justified.

In addition, encouraged by the positive and significant relationship of perceived safety and security with tourists' attitude and intention, resort practitioners must install security cameras, build good relations with the law enforcement agencies, have a proper emergency response plan, secure online data, maintain proper health and hygiene protocols, encourage the tourists to keep their valuables in the safe vaults of the resorts. If the resorts can properly ensure these safety measures, this will certainly inspire tourists to visit.

Lastly, as there is positive relationship between attitude and intention, resort marketers should constantly monitor the attitudes of their guests and try to build good relationships with them by enhancing their service performance.

7. Conclusion, Limitation, and Future Research Scopes

This research found that physical environment, perceived price justice, and perceived safety, perceived crowdedness are the crucial reasons that influence tourists' attitude and intention in the resort setting. However, perceived health and hygiene risks were found to have insignificant relationships with tourists. This is one of the first attempts that explored tourists' attitudinal and behavioral pattern in the resort setting from Bangladeshi context in the pandemic crisis.

However, this study contains several limitations. In this study, the researchers conducted a cross-sectional study, in which the resort tourists from only a few selected districts were selected. The authors believe that the findings can be further generalized by conducting a longitudinal study after taking respondents from other districts of Bangladesh which were not considered in this study. Moreover, this study considers only five predictors of attitude toward visiting. However, the authors believe that future studies should consider several other constructs, such as consumer emotion, experience, destination image, trust in social media reviews, for better understanding of tourists' attitude and behavior in the resort setting.

Finally, the authors believe that this study has made contributions to the tourism literature and theory by applying the behavioral reasoning theory to understand tourist attitude and behavioral intention in the resorts. The model showed adequate in-sample explanatory power. It is believed that the findings of this paper will certainly encourage the resort marketers to enhance their performance by stimulating tourist attitude and intention.

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Appendix:

Constructs	Items	Sources
Physical Environment	The resort's temperature is comfortable	Ali & Amin (2014)
	The resort's environment is clean	
	The resort's architecture is impressive	
	The colors within the resort are complementary and coordinating	
	Aesthetic view of the landscape was satisfactory	
Perceived Price Justice	The prices are reasonable	Ali & Amin (2014)
	The prices are fair	Cakici et al. (2019)
	The prices are appropriate	
	The prices are affordable	
Perceived Safety	Level of safety at daytime was adequate	George (2003)
	Walking after evening was safe	
	Using public transport was satisfactory	
	Roaming around the resort was secured	
	Accommodation facility had enough security protocol	
Perceived Crowding	The resort seemed very crowded	Milman et al. (2020)
	The area was too busy	
	I felt cramped visiting the resort	
Health & Hygiene Risks	I have a fear of being exposed to any contagious disease in the resort	Su et al. (2020)
	I might get sick if I visit any resort	
	I feel physically uncomfortable in the resort	
Attitude	Visiting resorts is so relaxing	Ajzen & Driver (1992)
	I have a positive mindset to visit resorts	
	I feel good when I visit resort	
	I believe visiting resorts are enjoyable	
Intention	I will visit this resort with my family members	Ajzen & Driver (1992)
	I intend to visit the resort in the next six months	
	I have plan to visit similar tourist attraction soon	
	I have a willingness to visit resorts in near future	
	I will make an effort to visit more and more resorts in the country	
	I am likely to spend time in any resort with my family in the next six months	